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Ranking of Countries by Government Effectiveness

The value of Government Effectiveness decreased by 8.37% on average between 2013 and 2021.

Government effectiveness captures perceptions of the quality of public services, the quality of the civil service and the degree of its independence from political pressures, the quality of policy formulation and implementation, and the credibility of government commitment to such policies. The estimate gives the country's score on the aggregate indicator, in units of a standard normal distribution, i.e. ranging from approximately -2.5 to 2.5.

Ranking of countries by value of government effectiveness in 2021. Singapore ranks first in value of government effectiveness with a value of 2.29, followed by Switzerland with a value of 2.03, Denmark with 2.00, Finland with 1.96 and Norway with 1.83. In the middle of the table are Romania with -0.12, Bulgaria with -0.13, Antigua and Barbuda with -0.14, Ghana with -0.14, Tunisia with -0.16, Russia with -0.17. In the last places are Venezuela with -1.85, Somalia with -2.05, Haiti with -2.18, Yemen with -2.30, South Sudan with -2.38.

Ranking of countries by value of percentage change in government effectiveness between 2013 and 2021. Jordan ranks first by value of percentage change in government effectiveness between 2013 and 2021 with a value of 218806.63%, followed by China with a value of 4359.59%, Rwanda with 1520.84%, Saudi Arabia with 601.85%, and Samoa with 569.08%. In the middle of the table are the Central African Republic with a value of -0.86%, followed by Moldova with -1.11%, Latvia with -1.29%, Malaysia with -1.54%, Norway with -2, 01%, Netherlands -2.35%. The ranking is closed by Belize with -234.36%, Brazil with -263.42, Lebanon with -329.52%, Armenia with -392.47%, Bulgaria with -796.70%, Suriname with -3491, 96%. On average, between 2013 and 2021, the value of Government Effectiveness decreased by a value equal to -8.37% for the countries considered.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with Elbow's Method. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method is presented below. Four clusters are identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: Burkina Faso, Pakistan, Guetamala, Zambia, Uganda, Honduras, Tanzania, Ethiopia, Cambodia, Papua New Guinea, Uzbekistan, Niger, Malawi, Bangladesh, Nicaragua, Ivory Coast, Kyrgyz Republic, Sao Tome and Principe, Eswatini, Lao Democratic Republic, Benin, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Gambia, Moldova, Belize, Bolivia, Paraguay, Tuvalu, Egypt Arab Rep., Vanuatu, Lesotho, Ukraine, Mozambique, Algeria, Cameroon, Gabon, Mauritania, Lebanon, Belarus, Kenya, Iran Islamic Rep., Ecuador, Suriname, Turkmenistan, Dominican Republic, Nauru, Nepal, Djibouti, Kiribati, Senegal, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Solomon Islands, Palau, El Salvador, Maldives, Guyana, Brazil, Mali, East Timor, Angola, Peru, Ghana, Guinea.
- Cluster 2: Australia, Austria, Germany, Iceland, Sweden, United Kingdom, United States, Japan, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Canada, Ireland, New Zealand, France, Netherlands,

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United Arab Emirates, Denmark, Andorra, Norway, Belgium, Israel, Switzerland, Finland, Singapore, Portugal, Brunei Darussalam, North Korea, Estonia, Slovenia, Spain, Lithuania, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Mauritius, Malaysia, Malta, Latvia, Chile, Barbados, Qatar.

- Cluster 3: Thailand, Costa Rica, Trinidad and Tobago, Greece, Saudi Arabia, Botswana, Oman, Namibia, Panama, Cape Verde, South Africa, Bahrain, Montenegro, Jordan, Philippines, Bhutan, China, St. Vincent and the Grenadines, St. Lucia, Jamaica, Rwanda, Italy, Turkey, India, Antigua and Barbuda, Bulgaria, Serbia, Uruguay, Vietnam, Croatia, Hungary, North Macedonia, Georgia, Indonesia, Albania, Colombia, St. Kittis and Nevis, Samoa, Dominica, Romania, Argentina, Seychelles, Mexico, Tunisia, Sri Lanka, Grenada, Poland, Tonga, Bahamas, Kuwait, Kazakhstan, Fiji, Slovak Republic, Cuba, Morocco, Russian Federation, Azerbaijan, Micronesia Fed. SS, Armenia.
- Cluster 4: Comoros, Eritrea, Congo Dem. Rep., Sudan, Guinea-Bissau, Chad, Syrian Arab Republic, Libya, Central African Republic, Marshall Islands, Korea Dem. People's Rep., Afghanistan, Haiti, Liberia, Yemen Rep., Venezuela, Somalia, South Sudan, Burundi, Zimbabwe, Congo Rep., Iraq, Madagascar, Sierra Leone, Equatorial Guinea, Myanmar, Nigeria, Togo.

From the point of view of the median, it appears that the first cluster in terms of Government Effectiveness value is C2. The following ordering is determined, i.e. $C2=1.3 > C3=0.19 > C1=-0.62 > C4=-1.54$.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Below is a comparison of eight different machine learning algorithms for predicting the future value of the meaning of Government Effectiveness. The algorithms are evaluated according to the maximization of the R-Squared value, the value of MAE, MSE and RMSE. The algorithms were trained with 80% of the data while the remaining 20% was used for the actual prediction. The ranking of the algorithms is identified below, namely:

- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value equal to 4;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 8;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 12;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression with a payoff value of 16;
- ANN with a payoff value of 20;
- PNN with a payoff value of 24;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 32.

Therefore using the Polynomial Regression it is possible to predict the following results in terms of predictive trend of Government Effectiveness or:

- Lebanon with 15.5%;
- Argentina with 5.7%;
- Mexico with 5.54%;
- North Macedonia with 5.48%;
- Algeria with 5.34%;
- Mali with 5.3%;
- Saint Kittis and Nevis with 4.92%;
- Djibouti with 3.3%;
- Belarus with 2.87%;
- Solomon Islands with 2.84%;
- Mauritius with 2.23%;

- Norway with 1.16%;
- Malaysia with 1.15%;
- Peru with 0.87%;
- Egypt with 0.83%;
- Australia with 0.79%;
- Zambia with 0.71%;
- Austria with 0.61%;
- Paraguay with 0.44%;
- Eritrea with 0.38%;
- Uganda with 0.23%;
- Bulgaria with -0.03%;
- Ivory Coast with -0.05%;
- Brunei Darussalam with -0.09%;
- Antigua and Barbuda and Greece with -0.33%;
- Cambodia with -0.38%;
- Mozambique with -0.56%;
- Dominica with -1.15%;
- Ghana with -1.16%;
- United Arab Emirates with -1.26%;
- Iraq with -1.55%;
- Hungary with -1.95%;
- Kenya with -2.11%;
- Ireland with -2.15%;
- Kuwait with -2.65%;
- Belgium with -2.69%;
- Equatorial Guinea with -3.03%;
- Jordan with -3.19%;
- Benin with -3.75%;
- Yemen with -5.67%;
- Zimbabwe with -5.77%;
- Seychelles with -6.59%;
- Madagascar -7.04%;
- Marshall Islands with -7.69%;
- Nigeria with -8.58%;
- Liberia with -8.65%;
- Tuvalu with -8.73%;
- Nepal with -9.00%;
- Angola with -9.27%;
- Guinea-Bissau with -9.28%;
- Gabon with -10.05%;
- Bhutan with -11.18%;
- Syrian Arab Republic with -11.79%;
- Maldives with -13.19%;
- Uzbekistan with -15.92%;
- Central African Republic with -19.07%;
- Libya with -24.84%.

On average, the predicted value is equal to -24.84%.

Conclusions. The value of government effectiveness grew on average globally between 2013 and 2021. However, there are significant global differences between countries as indicated by the cluster analysis. The leading countries in terms of government effectiveness are the Western countries. It follows that although there is a dimension of confrontation between the western world and the rest of the world, the level of effectiveness of the government of western civilization is unattainable for many growing Asian countries. In fact, it is necessary to consider the effects of economic growth and per capita income in the Asian world on the size of democratic institutions and on the levels of freedom of the population. In fact, although the Asian countries are growing, they remain very backward from the point of view of government effectiveness. And probably the further growth of Asian countries could encounter limits precisely because of the reduced levels of government effectiveness.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

